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CONTENT

Volume XV	No. 1	Dec. 2018
Sr. No.	Article and Author	Page No.s
1.	Hydrochemical Characteristics of Water Quality in Selected South Chennai Lakes, Tamil Nadu, 2015-16 M. Srirama Laxmi Devi, Thulasi Mala, D. and P. Mohana	1-10
2.	A Geographical study of voting Behaviour in Reserved Constituencies of Uttar Pradesh during 2017 Assembly Election Rohit Kumar and Arun K. Singh	11-21
3.	Solid Waste Management in Selected Indian Cities: A Geographical Analysis Tutun Hazra and Arun K. Singh	22-33
4.	Land Use and Cropping Pattern Change in Bareilly, UP: A Geographical Analysis Geeta Devi and Seema Tiwari	34-43
5.	An Assessment of Landuse Dynamics in Pallikaranai Wetlands, Tamil Nadu Leelvathy K. V., Madha Suresh V. and Vignesh K. S.	44-50
6.	Women Workforce Participation in Kushinagar, Uttar Pradesh Dilip Kumar Chaudhary and D. Gownamani	51-62
7.	Morphometric Analysis, Terrain Characteristics and Hydrological Dynamics of Birahi Ganga Basin in Chamoli District of Uttarakhand, India Gopinath Patra, Sucheta Mukherjee and Druheen Chakraborty	63-77
8.	Trend and Regional Imbalances of Urbanisation In U. P. - A Geographical Perspective Alok Kumar Choubey and Gayatri Rai	78-91
9.	Spatial Analysis of Sustainable Neighbourhood Mobility of Children in Mumbai Metropolitan Region Sumant Sovani	92-96
10.	Watersheds as Units of Integrated Regional Development: Overview of Some Case Studies in Goa Prabir Kumar Rath	97-107

WOMEN WORKFORCE PARTICIPATION IN KUSHINAGAR DISTRICT, UTTAR PRADESH

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Abstract

The present paper examines the trend, pattern and disparity of women workforce participation in Kushinagar district over the decade 2001 and 2011. The focus of the study is to examine the gap between men and women in main and marginal workers category over the decade. The study is based on secondary data sources and analysis is done by using excel sheets. The disparity index between male and female is calculated by Sopher's disparity index. The major finding of the paper shows that the trend of workforce in both main and marginal workers is decreasing for both male and female category. The disparity index shows that the inequality between male and female in main workers category is high in both the Census years. In marginal workers category the disparity in 2001 is very low where female shows better performance than male but the scenario is opposite in 2011 where female lagged far behind the male. The major reason for the lagging behind of female is due to the fact that the works in rural area are limited and women are generally confined to household works and most of the women cannot find jobs due to low skill levels and jobs in the non-farms sectors are also limited which led in withdrawing of women workforce to some extent. Women are paid low wages than men for the same work and that is why many of them do not prefer to work. For the inclusive development of the region as well as country it is necessary that each and every section of the society should get equal jobs/employments opportunities.

Key words : Workforce, Main Workers, Marginal Workers, Sopher's Disparity Index.

Introduction

Workforce participation in Kushinagar district of U. P. is decreasing with each passing decade. Here, the women (work) participation in the district is lagging far behind (than) men in both main and marginal workers category at present. The inequality in workforce can be seen spatially as well as temporally in different blocks. The unequal workforce participation is one of the barrier in the inclusive development of the district.

Women in India are paid low when it comes to participation in labour force and for that social norms play important role in creating barriers in their mobility, lower level of educational attainment and lack in formal sectors opportunities (Chaudhary and Verick, 2014). Women comprise 48.5% of the total population of India and their participation in agriculture sector is largest as far as employment is concerned. In the rural areas, 59% men work in agriculture, but when it comes to women it stands as 75%, which is quite higher than the male counterpart (NSSO). Women's participation in agriculture has been increasing significantly than men which plays important role in increasing dependence on women in agricultural sector, it also reveals their importance in the sustainable growth and future of agricultural sector. Women in the workforce earning wages or salary are part of a modern phenomenon, one that developed at the same time as the growth of paid employment for men, but women have been challenged by

inequality in the workforce. Women's lack of access to higher education had effectively excluded them from the practice of well-paid and high status occupations. The wage earning characteristics of women has been improved in respect to men but the discriminatory component of gender wage gap has also been increased, but if the women are paid like men then they would earn more than men use to earn (Deshpande, Goal and Khanna, 2018). In rural areas total female workers are increasing in agricultural activities (Suneeta, 2014).

In India, female workforce participation rate is one of the lowest in the world especially when it comes to urban population (Balla and Kaur, 2011). The agricultural land ownership for women is mere a record as the main power lie in the hand of male counterpart though female get the inheritance of land ownership through purchase or familial inheritance but they are only instruments, it largely remain in the hand of male (Parwez, 2012). The gender gap in the land ownership can be minimized by inheriting women equally as men inherited not only inheritance but also the actually decision making power (Arora and Singhi, 2009). Wherever there is agricultural land ownership for women, they belong to tenancy so they either sell out the agricultural land or lease out (Jassal, 2001).

The decreasing rate of men's participation in agriculture has boosted an increase in women's participation in share of agricultural workforce and it has expanded the women's role in this sector. However, with absorption of labour in agricultural workforce, it is in decline especially in paid jobs, about two third of the women workers are self-employed, they work as managers and helpers in their family farm without any remuneration. Here, the one who continue as daily worker earn wage very little than the statutory minimum. Hence women in this agricultural workforce face increasing responsibility in providing food security for the household under the unfavourable economic condition and their work burden (Aruna, 2010).

Study Area

Kushinagar district is a part of Gorakhpur division in eastern Uttar Pradesh, its district headquarter is located at Padrauna town. The district is famous for the Mahaparinirvana of Mahatma Buddha. Since 13th May, 1994, the district came into existence, earlier it was a part of Deoria district.

The district has an area of 2,905 square kilometres, it is bounded by Bihar State in the East, Deoria in the South, Gorakhpur district on the West and Mahariganj district in the North-West. The climate in the district remain extremely hot in summer and moderately cold during the winter season. At present, the district has been divided into 6 sub divisions including Padrauna, Kasia, Hata, Tamkuhi Raj, Khadda and Kaptanganj. The district has been also divided into fourteen Community Development Blocks namely Kaptanganj, Ramkola, Motichak, Hata, Sukrauli, Khadda, Nebuwa Naurangiya, Vishunpura, Padrauna, Kasiya, Dudhai, Fazil nagar, Tamkuhi and Sevarahi.

According to the 2011 census Kushinagar district has a population of 35, 64,544 persons in which 18, 18,055 are males and 17, 46,489 are females. The district has a sex ratio of 961 females per 1000 males. The district has a population density of 1226 inhabitants per square kilometre. Its population growth rate over the decade 2001-2011 was 23.08% in which 23.37% are male growth rate whereas female has a growth rate of 23.03%. The district has made a slight progress in the field of education through various progressive steps. The district has a total literacy rate as 67.25% in which female literacy rate is 52.36% whereas male literacy rate is 77.71%. Agriculture is the backbone as far as economy is concerned. People are engaged in agriculture because the industrialization is negligible in the district.

of male workforce participation, i.e., $X_2 \geq X_1$, Here, it is noted that in 2001 the female workforce in marginal workers has greater than male so X_2 is taken for female workforce participation and X_1 is taken for male workforce participation (marginal workers of 2001 only). Higher the value of Disparity Index will show the higher inequality in genders and lower the Disparity will show the lesser inequality between the genders. The perfect equality between the genders will be at zero Disparity Index. Hence, Sopher's Disparity Index is very useful in measuring the relative disparity. The study has focussed on rural population only and urban population has been excluded.

Spatial Pattern of Workforce Participation, 2001

In Kushinagar district, the total main workers comprise of 19.8% in which male has 32.3% and female has 6.9% participation in 2001. Whereas participation in total marginal workers is 14.8% in which male has 13.3% and female has 16.4% participation. Here, female has better participation as marginal workers than males because female work as agricultural labourer for the short time period whereas males used to migrate to the urban centres. Table 1 shows that Nebua Naurangiya (23.3%) has the highest main workforce participation in the district whereas Tamkuhi Raj (16.6%) has the lowest workforce participation. The male participation in main workers category shows that Khadda (35.2%) has the highest

Table 1: Spatial pattern of workforce participation (main and marginal workers), 2001

Blocks (2001)	main workers	male	female	Gap	marginal workers	Male	female	Gap
Khadda	22.9	35.2	9.6	25.6	15.0	13.2	17.0	-3.8
Nebua Naurangiya	23.3	34.7	11.1	23.6	17.5	13.9	21.3	-7.4
Vishunpura	20.9	34.3	6.3	28.0	15.6	13.0	18.3	-5.3
Padrauna	18.4	30.4	5.8	24.6	14.5	14.4	14.5	-0.1
Kaptanganj	20.5	33.1	7.2	25.9	12.9	12.2	13.6	-1.4
Ramkola	20.4	32.9	7.1	25.8	15.6	13.4	17.9	-4.5
Motichak	18.6	31.0	6.2	24.8	17.0	15.2	18.9	-3.7
Sukrauli	18.7	30.3	6.9	23.4	19.8	16.7	22.9	-6.2
Hata	19.7	33.2	6.2	27.0	14.5	11.8	17.3	-5.5
Kasiya	18.5	31.5	4.8	26.7	12.6	11.5	13.7	-2.2
Fazilnagar	16.9	29.7	4.5	25.2	14.0	12.2	15.7	-3.5
Tamkuhi Raj	16.6	28.4	5.0	23.4	12.3	13.0	11.6	1.4
Dudhahi	20.9	33.9	7.3	26.6	14.5	12.9	16.2	-3.3
Sevrahi	21.6	34.0	8.8	25.2	13.4	12.9	14.0	-1.1
Total	19.8	32.3	6.9	25.4	14.8	13.3	16.4	-3.1

Source: District Census Handbook Kushinagar, 2001

participation whereas Tamkuhi Raj (28.4%) has the lowest share in main workers category. In the female category of main workers Nebua Naurangiya (11.1%) has the highest share while Fazilnagar (4.5%) has the lowest participation rate. The highest gap between male and female main workforce participation has been found in Vishunpura (28%) block while lowest gap has been found in Tamkuhi Raj (23.4%) and Sukrauli (23.4%) blocks. All the blocks have a gap more than 23% which is quite high and depicting the inequality in workforce participation rate in main workers category. The reasons behind the inequality between male and female workers in all the blocks are male has the better right as cultivators, most of the females are housewives (architecture of house) who do not considered as workers, female are lagging behind in education, social restrictions i.e. most of the female remain at home and not allowed to work outside, etc.

Table 1 reflects that the total marginal workers comprise of 14.8% in which total male and female marginal workers were 13.3% and 16.4% respectively in 2001. There is a gap of 3.1% between female and male marginal workers, it shows that female fare a better participation in marginal workers in 2001 Census. The spatial pattern in the district shows that the highest male marginal workers recorded in Sukrauli (16.7%) whereas lowest found in Kasiya (11.5%). The highest female marginal workers found in Sukrauli (22.9%) and lowest in Tamkuhi Raj (11.6%). So the data reveals that almost all the blocks has more female participation than male except Tamkuhi Raj (1.4%). So the share of marginal workers in 2001 shows that female participation is better than male because female work as seasonal workers whereas male workers work for major part of the years.

Spatial pattern of workforce participation, 2011

Table 2 shows that in 2011 the total main workers were 14.5% in which total male workers were 22.8% and female workers were 5.8%, so a large gap (17%) can be observed between male and female. The spatial pattern in the district of main workers shows that Ramkola (18%) has the highest share of main work participation whereas Tamkuhi Raj (10.5%) has the lowest participation. The highest main male workers has been found in Ramkola (28.9%) and lowest in Tamkuhi Raj (17%). The highest percentage of female main workers found in Sukrauli (8.4%) and lowest in Tamkuhi Raj (4%). The highest gap between male and female main workers is found in Ramkola (22.4%) and lowest in Tamkuhi Raj (13%).

The table 2 also shows that the participation of marginal workers, it fare a better share in workforce participation than the main workers. The total marginal workers recorded as 17.1% in the district in which male comprised of 21.5% and female comprised of 12.5% during the 2011 Census. The spatial pattern in the district shows that Khadda (21.3%) has the highest participation of marginal workers while Ramkola 13.4% has the lowest participation (table 2). The highest male marginal workers has been recorded in Khadda (25.7%) and lowest in Ramkola (16.5%) whereas highest female marginal work participation has been found in Khadda (16.6%) and lowest recorded in Padrauna (9.5%) and Fazilnagar (9.5%) during 2011 Census. The highest and lowest gap has been found in Fazilnagar (12.7%) and Sukrauli (3.7%) respectively.

The marginal workers has been increased in comparison to main workers over the years not only in the district but also in the state so as in the country as well. The reason behind the decrease in workforce participation rate is that the population growth has been decelerated so as the workforce participation. The increase in educational demand affect the labour force to

(26)

Table 2: Spatial pattern of workforce participation (main and marginal workers), 2011

Blocks (2011)	main workers	male	Female	Gap	marginal workers	male	Female	gap
Khadda	13.9	21.0	6.3	14.7	21.3	25.7	16.6	9.1
Nebua								
Naurangiya	15.2	24.5	5.2	19.3	16.3	20.7	11.6	9.1
Vishunpura	15.1	24.1	5.8	18.3	16.5	20.4	12.5	7.9
Padrauna	14.7	23.6	5.4	18.2	14.8	19.6	9.5	10.1
Kaptanganj	15.6	25.2	5.7	19.5	15.4	20.3	10.4	9.9
Ramkola	18.0	28.9	6.5	22.4	13.4	16.5	10.2	6.3
Motichak	15.1	24.0	6.1	17.9	17.8	21.9	13.7	9.3
Sukrauli	16.4	24.4	8.4	16	21.1	23.0	19.3	3.7
Hata	15.9	25.6	6.2	19.4	14.7	17.8	11.7	6.1
Kasiya	14.1	21.9	6.0	15.9	16.0	20.9	10.9	10.0
Fazilnagar	11.7	19.0	4.3	14.7	15.9	22.2	9.5	12.7
Tamkuhi Raj	10.5	17.0	4.0	13.0	19.2	24.8	13.5	11.3
Dudhahi	12.9	19.5	5.9	13.6	19.5	23.8	14.9	8.9
Sevrahi	14.7	22.8	6.2	16.6	17.6	22.5	12.4	10.1
Total	14.5	22.8	5.8	17.0	17.1	21.5	12.5	9.0

Source: District Census Handbook Kushinagar, 2011

drop out from work which might be considered as a welcome step; also the job opportunities are not increasing which caused a high unemployment rate. The female workforce in both main and marginal workers category is decreasing than male counterparts. The shifting of the workers from main to marginal workers category happened because of MGNREGA which provide work for a short period of time (100 days). The females are lagging far behind males in both main and marginal workers but the inequality is high in main workers category because females work for a short period of time, the house work do not consider as workforce and most of the female remained as house workers.

Trend of Main workers (male and female) in Kushinagar district, U.P.

The figure 2 shows that the male main workers have been divided in three class intervals as lowest (below 23%), medium (23%-29%) and higher (above 29%) in 2001 and 2011. The male main workers have higher participation i.e. more than 29% in almost all the blocks except Tamkuhi Raj which has lowest category of main workforce participation. But in 2011 the higher category of main work participation is not found in any blocks indicating that the main workforce

in all the blocks has been decreased. The medium category of main workforce is found in Nebua Naurangiya, Vishunpura, Kaptaininganj, Ramkola, Padrauna, Motichak, Sukrauli and Hata whereas lowest category of main workers are found in Khadda, Dudhahi, Kasiya, Tamkuhi Raj, Fazilnagar and Sevrahi. So the trend of male main workers is decreasing because of the low job opportunities, shifting of workers in marginal workers category and education attainment (keeping away the younger section of the society from labour force). The female main workers lagging far behind the male.

Fig. 2: Trend of Main Workers Participation in Kushinagar, 2001-2011

The female main workers have been categorized in three class intervals lower (below 6%), medium (6%-9%) and higher (above 9%). The higher category of female work participation in 2001 has been found in two blocks i.e. Khadda and Nebua Naurangiya whereas medium category of female work participation of main workers has been recorded in Vishunpura, Kaptaininganj, Ramkola, Motichak, Sukrauli, Hata, Dudhahi and Sevrahi; the lower category of female work participation has been recorded in the Padrauna, Tamkuhi Raj, Kasiya and Fazilnagar. According to 2011 Census, the higher category of female work participation has not found in any block. The medium category of female work participation has been recorded in Khadda, Ramkola, Hata, Sukrauli, Motichak and Sevrahi whereas the lowest category of female work participation of main workers has been recorded in Nebua Naurangiya, Kaptaininganj, Vishunpura, Padrauna, Kasiya, Fazilnagar, Tamkuhi Raj and Dudhahi (Fig. 2). Here the trend of female main workers is declining in almost all the blocks because most of the females are not working anymore or indulging as agricultural workers who mainly use to work for short period of time as seasonal workers.

Trend of Marginal Workers (male and female) in Kushinagar district, U.P.

The figure 3 shows that the male marginal workers have been divided in three class intervals lower (below 16%), medium (16%-21%) and highest (above 21%). The higher category of male marginal workers has not recorded in any blocks in 2001 whereas only one block Sukrauli has recorded in the medium category, apart from this all the blocks have recorded low male workforce participation in 2001. But in 2011 Census, apart from Ramkola all the blocks have shown an increase in male marginal workers. The higher category of male marginal workers have been recorded in Khadda, Motichak, Sukrauli, Dudhahi, Sevrahi, Fazilnagar and Tamkahu Raj, while the medium category of male marginal workers are found in Nebua Naurangiya, Vishunpura, Padrauna, Kaptanganj, Kasiya and Hata whereas the lowest category of male marginal workers has been found in only one block i.e. Ramkola. Here, it has been found that all the blocks have been improved when it comes to participation of marginal workers because majority of the workers work for a short period of time due to unavailability of permanent works. Most of the workers work as seasonal labourers. Agricultural workers work for short period of time due to seasonal cropping pattern in the Kushinagar region (specially the cultivation season of sugarcane).

The figure 3 also shows that the female marginal workers participation have been categorised in three categories, i.e. lowest (below 15%), medium (15%-20%) and highest (above 20%). According to 2001 Census the highest category of female marginal workers have been recorded in Nebua Naurangiya and Sukrauli, medium in seven blocks i.e. Khadda, Vishunpura, Ramkola,

Fig. 3: Trend of Marginal Workers Participation in Kushinagar, 2001-2011

WOMEN WORKFORCE PARTICIPATION IN KUSHINAGAR DISTRICT, UTTAR PRADESH

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Dilip

Motichak, Hata, Dudhahi and Fazilnagar whereas lowest category of female marginal workers have been recorded in Kaptainganj, Padrauna, Kasiya, Tamkuhi Raj and Sevrahi. In both 2001 and 2011 Census, the higher category of female marginal workers has been recorded in the Sevrahi block, whereas Motichak has recorded in the medium category in 2001 but apart from these two blocks all the other 12 blocks have recorded in the lowest category of female marginal work participation in 2011 Census. The figure 3 also shows that there is a decrease in female marginal workers from 2001 to 2011 Census because females are more engaged to house work which is not considered as workforce, also the male workers are replacing the works of female in main as well as marginal workers category. Here, the main and marginal workforce in both male and female category have been decreasing over the decade which is not a good sign for the development of the region as well as for the state and country.

Disparity index in male and female, 2001-2011

The disparity in workforce shows that the inequality between male and female workers. The higher the value of disparity index, the greater is the inequality between male and female whereas lower the disparity index shows lower inequality or it shows equality between them. In 2001 and 2011 Census the disparity index of main workers in Kushinagar district has been recorded as 0.81 and 0.68 respectively which is quite high, showing high inequality between male and female in main workers category. Whereas the disparity in marginal workers during 2001 and 2011 Census recorded as 0.11 and 0.29 which is low and showing a less inequality between male and female. The 2001 Census shows that the female fare better than male in marginal workers category. The spatial pattern of the disparity index of main male and female workers in 2001 show that Kasiya (0.96) has the highest disparity index whereas Nebua Naurangiya (0.63) has the lowest disparity index. In the year 2011, the highest disparity index has been recorded in Ramkola (0.78) whereas lowest disparity index has been found in Sukrauli (0.55) block.

The disparity index of marginal workers in 2001 recorded that the males are lagging behind females in the blocks, where all the blacks has female marginal work participation more than the male workers. The disparity between female and male marginal workers is highest in Nebua Naurangiya (0.22) whereas lowest has been recorded in Padrauna (0.04) and Sukrauli (0.04). But in 2011 the disparity index of marginal workers has again shown a bigger disparity between male and female. Block-wise analysis of the disparity index of marginal workers in 2011 has been recorded highest in Fazilnagar (0.43) and lowest in Sukrauli (0.10). So it is clear from the data analysis that in 2001 males lagged behind female in marginal workers category but in 2011 the situation inversed and females lagged far behind males. The disparity between male and female is caused by the fact that most of the males do not allow their female counter part to work when they get work to do.

The disparity index of main workers has been divided into three class intervals, i.e. low (below 0.70), medium (0.70-0.85) and high (above 0.85). According to 2001 Census, higher category of disparity of main workers has been recorded in Vishunpura, Hata, Kasiya, Tamkuhi Raj and Fazilnagar, whereas the medium category of disparity index has been recorded in Khadda, Kaptainganj, Ramkola, Motichak, Sukrauli, Padrauna, Dudhahi and Sevrahi, while the lowest category of disparity has been recorded in Nebua Naurangiya (fig.4). But in 2011, the highest category of disparity does not found in any block. The medium category of disparity index has been recorded in Nebua Naurangiya, Vishunpura, Kaptainganj, Ramkola, Padrauna, Hata and

Table 3: Disparity Index in Workforce Participation (male-female), 2001-2011

Blocks	Disparity Index (main Workers)		Disparity index (marginal workers)	
	2001	2011	2001	2011
Khadda	0.71	0.60	0.13	0.28
Nebua Naurangiya	0.63	0.76	0.22	0.30
Vishunpura	0.89	0.71	0.18	0.25
Padrauna	0.85	0.73	0.04	0.37
Kaptanganj	0.77	0.75	0.10	0.34
Ramkola	0.81	0.78	0.15	0.23
Motichak	0.83	0.69	0.12	0.25
Sukrauli	0.77	0.55	0.15	0.10
Hata	0.88	0.72	0.20	0.21
Kasiya	0.96	0.64	0.09	0.34
Fazilnagar	0.95	0.72	0.13	0.43
Tamkuhi Raj	0.88	0.69	0.06	0.33
Dudhahi	0.80	0.59	0.11	0.25
Sevrahi	0.73	0.65	0.04	0.31
Total	0.81	0.68	0.11	0.29

Source: Computed by Author from District Census Handbook, Kushinagar, 2001 and 2011

Fazilnagar whereas the lowest category has been recorded in Khadda, Motichak, Sukrauli, Kasiya, Dudhahi, Tamkuh Raj and Sevrahi. The disparity has been decreased during the last decade in almost all the blocks except Nebua Naurangiya which has shown slight increase in disparity in main workers category. The disparity in main workers was high in 2001 because males used to do all the works keeping female for less participation but in 2011 the scenario has improved at somewhat extent that the participation of female as main workers has increased.

The fig. 4 shows the disparity index of marginal male and female workers and the index values are divided into three categories which are low (below 0.15), medium (0.15-0.30), and high (above 0.30). Here, in 2001 the disparity index of marginal workers category recorded very low but females fare better than males.

The higher category of disparity index of marginal workers in 2001 has not been recorded in any blocks but in 2011 it has been recorded in Kaptanganj, Padrauna, Kasiya, Tamkuhi Raj, Fazilnagar and Sevrahi. The medium category of disparity index of marginal workers in 2001 has been recorded in Nebua Naurangiya, Hata and Vishunpura but the participation of females were higher than males whereas in 2011 it has been recorded in Khadda, Ramkola, Nebua Naurangiya, Hata, Vishunpura, Motichak and Dudhahi. In 2001, the lowest category of disparity index is found in almost all the blocks but males were lagging behind females whereas in 2011 the disparity index again shows the male dominance in marginal work participation while the lowest category of disparity index has recorded only in Sukrauli.

Dilip

Source: Computed by author from District Census Handbook, Kushinagar, 2001 and 2011

Fig. 4: Disparity Index of Workforce participation between male and female

From the analysis of the above data it is clear that the disparity between male and female in main workers category is high where females were lagging far behind in equality but in marginal workers category males were lagging behind than females in 2001 but again in 2011 they dominated female counter part in terms of marginal work participation. The inequality in main workers category is due to the fact that female work participation is very low and they mainly work for a short period of time as marginal workers and that is why the disparity is also low.

Conclusion

The women workforce participation has been influenced by multidimensional factor among them the level of education, economic class, social structure of the society, availability of firms and other types of employment opportunities available in that particular region, etc. There is found a wage gap between men and women workers which also caused the marginalization of women. The findings of the paper reveals that the trend of workforce participation has been decreasing significantly over the years. The disparity between male and female workforce participation is high in main workers category whereas the disparity is low in marginal workers category. The high inequality between male and female in main workers category is due to the fact that women work for a shorter period of time and they work majorly as agricultural labourers which is seasonal in nature. The low disparity in marginal workers category is due to the fact that most of the men are engaged in main workers category in district Kushinagar. The workforce participation of women is higher than the men in 2001 Census which has been highly decreased in 2011 where women again lagged far behind men in marginal workers category. The work

opportunities in rural area are limited and women are generally confined to household works and most of them cannot find jobs due to low skill levels, jobs in the non-farm sectors are also limited which led to the present scenario of lower work participation of women. Women are paid low wages for equal works as men and it is one of the reason that so many of them do not prefer to work. The MGNREGS has played a vital role in providing 100 days employment for both men and women which is also an important reason of the low disparity rate between male and female marginal workers. Though government has formulated many job providing programs and policies for both male and female in rural areas such as MGNREGA, PMEGP, PMM, etc. but it need a thorough implementation. So for the inclusive development of any region or country it is necessary that women and men are equally employed and should be given equal job opportunities.

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WOMEN WORKFORCE PARTICIPATION IN
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